

A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE PARENTAL KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS REGARDING THALASSEMIA IN NAWABSHAH

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Abstract

Background: Thalassemia is a lifelong inherited blood disorder that remains a major health problem in Pakistan. This study was carried out to evaluate the level of parental knowledge and awareness regarding Thalassemia in Nawabshah. A cross-sectional survey was conducted among 183 parents of Thalassemia patients visiting the Thalassemia Center Nawabshah. That most parents (63.68%) had poor knowledge, while only 36.72% demonstrated satisfactory awareness.

Objective: The objectives of this study were to assess the level of parental knowledge about Thalassemia.

Material and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Thalassemia Center, Nawabshah, after obtaining ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). The study aimed to assess parental knowledge and awareness regarding Thalassemia. A total of 183 parents of diagnosed Thalassemia patients were included in the study. Participants were selected through a systematic sampling technique to ensure appropriate representation of the target population. Parents who were willing to participate and available during the data collection period were enrolled after obtaining informed consent. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, and confidentiality of participants was strictly maintained throughout the research process.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 35.19 years with a standard deviation of 6.564. The majority of the participants were female (124, 67%) and predominantly belonged to the lower socioeconomic class (154, 84.2%). Most participants were Sindhi (123, 67.2%), and more than half of the respondents were illiterate (56%). Regarding occupation, the majority were housewives (123, 67.2%). The assessment of knowledge and awareness about thalassemia revealed that 63.68% of participants had poor knowledge, while 36.72% demonstrated good knowledge.

Conclusion: This study concludes that parental knowledge and awareness regarding Thalassemia in Nawabshah are generally inadequate. Most parents lack proper understanding of disease inheritance, preventive strategies, treatment options, and long-term complications. Low education, rural residence, and poor socioeconomic conditions were major factors associated with poor awareness. Strengthening health education, genetic counseling, and

community-based awareness programs is essential to reduce the burden of Thalassemia and prevent new cases in Pakistan.

INTRODUCTION

Blood disorders affect millions of people globally, and Thalassemia is recognized as one of the most common and serious inherited condition, A group of inherited blood defects is known as Thalassemia is among the world's most prevalent hemoglobinopathies, Thalassemias are of two types such as Alpha and Beta Thalassemia, The cause of these defects is gene mutations leading to low levels and/or malfunctioning α and β globin proteins, respectively, In some cases, one of these proteins may be completely absent. α and β globin chains form a globin fold attachment to carry oxygen, Genes for alpha and beta-globin proteins are present in the form of a cluster on chromosome 16 and 11, respectively, Different globin genes are used at different stages in the life course, During embryonic and fetal developmental stages, γ globin proteins partner with α globin and are later replaced by β globin protein. Globin chain imbalances result in hemolysis and impede erythropoiesi.

You will receive two of these genes from each of your parent, Your symptoms will vary depending on the number of affected or deleted genes, If someone inherits, One mutated gene, They are considered silent carriers and don't have symptoms but pass the disease to their kids, Two mutated genes, They will experience mild signs and symptoms of anemia, also known as the alpha-Thalassemia trait. Three mutated genes: Patients with these will experience moderate to severe anemia, also known as Haemoglobin H disease, Four mutated genes represent the most severe form, alpha-Thalassemia major, Unfortunately, babies with this condition usually die before birth or shortly after three mutated genes: Patients with these will experience moderate to severe anemia, also known as Haemoglobin H disease, Four mutated genes represent the most severe form, alpha-Thalassemia major, Unfortunately, babies with this condition usually die before birth or shortly after.

Symptoms typically appear within the first two years of life and may include features of severe anemia like dizziness and fast heart rate, along with other health issues such as Pale or yellow

skin, The skin may look pale due to severe anemia or yellow from the increased breakdown of red blood cells, Tiredness is often the first symptom of anemia, Behavioral changes, Anemia can make the child feel listless, fussy, or tired. Delayed puberty Children with Beta-Thalassemia major typically do not grow and gain weight as expected, and they may not have the expected growth spurt during puberty.

Thalassemia treatment varies by severity but typically includes blood transfusions to manage anemia and iron chelation therapy to remove excess iron from regular transfusions, For severe cases, stem cell transplants (bone marrow transplants) or newer gene therapies can offer a potential cure by providing a source of normal hemoglobin, Other options include medications like hydroxyurea and along with Folic acid supplements

Early detection before marriage and genetic screening are necessary to stop or reduce the escalation of this genetic disease.

Each year worldwide, around 60,000 symptomatic individuals are born out of 80-90 million Thalassemia carriers, This disease is one of the most prevalent chronic genetic diseases in the world and the Iran. About two hundred million people are afflicted with this disease all over the world.

Historically, the prevalence of β -Thalassemia has been highest in the Mediterranean region, the Middle East, and Southeast Asia and lowest in Northern Europe and North America, Due to migration patterns, β -Thalassemia is increasingly more common in non-endemic regions, including Western Europe and North America.⁴ According to a 2008 report from the World Health Organization, more than 40 000 infants are born with β -Thalassemia each year, of whom about 25 500 have transfusion-dependent β -thalassemia. The annual numbers of expected newborns with β -Thalassemia are 20 420 in Southeast Asia, 9914 in the Eastern Mediterranean region, 1019 in Europe, and 341 in North, Central, and South Americas, In Belgium, the incidence is 1 in 25 000 neonates. Approximately 150 million people who are carriers of Thalassemia live in the

Mediterranean countries, the Arabian peninsula, the Middle East countries, the west of Africa, Iran, Pakistan, Afghanistan, India, and Southeast Asia, Today, due to global migration and ethnic interactions, β Thalassemia can be encountered in all parts of the world.

In Pakistan 1-4 out of 1000 infants have the disease, There is no National registry but it is estimated that annual reported cases of Beta-Thalassemia are more than 4,000, Estimated Beta-Thalassemia carrier rate is around 5.3%, with certain regional variation between 1.8 and 8.0%.8-10 Incidence of beta Thalassemia trait in Muzaffarabad is 5.6%,11 Azad Kashmir is a remote mountainous area with difficult hilly terrains of 13,297 Km² and a population of 4,567,982 inhabitants, Consanguineous marriages are quiet common in Pakistani culture,12-14 In Kashmiri culture it is even more common, Consanguinity in the presence of high gene frequency, and high birth rate, along with large population size constitute significant risk factors, Pakistani population is at high risk but has poor public knowledge about the disease.

MATERIAL & METHODS

A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Thalassemia Center, Nawabshah, after obtaining ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB). The study aimed to assess parental knowledge and awareness regarding Thalassemia. A total of 183 parents of diagnosed Thalassemia patients were included in the study. Data collection was over two months of period of time from 17 November to 17 January 2026 after approval of IRB (Institutional Review Board) of PUMHSW. Sample size was 287 calculated by Yamane Formula with 95% confidence level and 5% of margin error. Participants were selected through a systematic sampling technique to ensure appropriate representation of the target population. Parents who were willing to participate and available during the data collection period were enrolled after obtaining informed consent. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, and confidentiality of participants was strictly maintained throughout the research process.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Age status of Respondents

Table 1: Gender status of Respondents

Gender	Frequency	Percentage%
Male	59	32.2 %
Female	124	67.8 %

Total	183	100.0
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Table 2: Residence status of respondent

Residence	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	51	27.9%
Rural	132	72.1%
Total	183	100.0

Table 3: Economic status of respondent

Economic	Frequency	Percentage
Poor class	154	84.2%
Middle class	29	15.8%
Total	183	100.0

Table 4 : Ethnicity status of respondent

Ethnicity	Frequency	Percentage
Sindhi	123	67.2%
Panjabi	33	18.0%
Baloch	19	10.4%
Pakhtoon	6	3.3%
Muhajir	2	1.1%
Total	183	100.0%

Figure 2: Education status of respondents

Table 5: Occupation status of respondent

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Shopkeeper	11	6.0%
Farmer	17	9.3%

Labour	30	16.4%
Housewife	123	67.2%
Other	2	1.1%
Total	183	100.0

Section B

Table 6: Parental Knowledge and awareness about Thalassemia

Questions	Aware	Not Aware
Have you ever heard of Thalassemia?	120(66%)	63(34%)
Individuals, who have Thalassemia major, are anemic?	100(55%)	83(45%)
Can a Patient survive if Thalassemia is left untreated?	73(40%)	110(60%)
Can Thalassemia be identified by a blood test?	64(35%)	119(65%)
Inter family marriages may lead to thalassemia?	70(39%)	113(61%)
Can conditions like fainting, fever, anemia, diarrhea, and vomiting worsen Thalassemia major?	77(43%)	106(57%)
Is blood transfusion a treatment modality for Thalassemia?	57(32%)	126(68%)
Individuals, who have Thalassemia major, lead normal lives with appropriate treatment?	73(40%)	110(60%)
Is Thalassemia a disease of the blood?	61(34%)	122(66%)
Can Thalassemia be only treated with medications?	63(35%)	120(65%)
If one parent has Thalassemia minor (is a carrier), the couple has a chance of having a child with Thalassemia disease?	70(39%)	113(61%)
Do both parents need to have Thalassemia minor for the baby to be born with Thalassemia major?	71(39%)	112(61%)

Table 7: Parental Knowledge and awareness about Thalassemia

Questions	Aware	Not Aware
Do you think Thalassemia is preventable?	65(36%)	118(64%)
Thalassemia is a contagious disease (you can catch it like a cold)?	58(32%)	125(68%)
Is chelation a treatment modality for Thalassemia?	60(33%)	123(67%)
Is Thalassemia an inherited disorder?	60(33%)	123(67%)
Would you say that children with Thalassemia major are more likely to develop (transfusion-related reactions, kidney failure and stroke)?	83(45%)	100(55%)
Are there different types of Thalassemia?	54(30%)	129(70%)
Does a person with Thalassemia minor lead a healthy life?	48(26%)	135(74%)
Thalassemia can be treated with surgery?	60(33%)	123(67%)
Is a specific type of food a treatment modality for Thalassemia?	70(38%)	113(62%)
Is bed rest a treatment modality for Thalassemia?	54(30%)	129(70%)
Is there a cure for Thalassemia major?	48(26%)	135(74%)
The problems in thalassemia major are due to iron overload and low blood transfusion?	60(33%)	123(77%)
Does Thalassemia lead to other diseases like diseases of the heart, liver, bones, spleen and lungs?	48(26%)	135(74%)

Figure 3: Knowledge level of the study Participants

DISCUSSION:

The present study assessed parental knowledge and awareness about Thalassemia in Pakistan, including demographic factors such as age, gender, residence, education, occupation, economic status, and ethnicity. The mean age of respondents was 35.19 years. The majority of participants were female (67.8%), rural residents (72.1%), and from a poor economic background (84.2%). Most participants were illiterate (56%), and the predominant ethnicity was Sindhi (67.2%). A large proportion of respondents were housewives (67.2%), followed by laborers (16.4%) and farmers (9.3%). Analysis of parental knowledge revealed overall poor awareness, with 63.68% classified as having poor knowledge and only 36.72% showing good knowledge. Awareness of specific aspects of Thalassemia was low: only 33% knew it is an inherited disorder, 32% recognized blood transfusion as treatment, 36% believed it is preventable, and 26–45% were aware of complications associated with the disease. Questions regarding premarital transmission, treatment with medications, and the role of chelation therapy also had low correct responses (26–39%).

These findings are consistent with previous studies in Pakistan. Manzoor and Zakar (2021), reported that while some parents had awareness about disease transmission, gaps existed in understanding prevention and genetic counseling found that parents recognized Thalassemia as hereditary, but their knowledge of treatment and preventive

measures was limited reported that a large proportion of parents were unaware of Thalassemia complications, which aligns with our findings where knowledge about health risks was low also highlighted low awareness regarding premarital and prenatal screening, similar to our observation that only 36% of parents knew about preventive aspects. The study found no significant difference in knowledge between male and female parents, indicating that awareness is independent of gender. However, sociodemographic factors such as rural residence, poor economic status, low education, and illiteracy appear to influence parental knowledge negatively, consistent with previous research. For instance, low literacy and rural background were associated with poorer understanding of Thalassemia in studies (2023). Overall, the study emphasizes the urgent need for targeted awareness programs, health education, and genetic counseling, especially for rural, low-income, and illiterate populations. Educating parents about inheritance, treatment, complications, and preventive measures is essential to reduce the prevalence and impact of Thalassemia in Pakistan. The analysis of knowledge levels showed that 63.68% of participants had poor knowledge, while only 36.72% demonstrated good understanding of the disease. This indicates that a majority of parents are not fully informed about the genetic risks, preventive strategies, and treatment options for thalassemia. In high-prevalence populations, such as those in Sindh, low

awareness poses a significant public health concern, as it may increase the likelihood of children being born with thalassemia major. These findings are consistent with previous studies in Pakistan and other high-burden countries, where parental knowledge about thalassemia remains inadequate, emphasizing the need for structured educational interventions, premarital counseling, and community awareness programs.

CONCLUSION:

The present study provides valuable insights into parental knowledge and awareness about Thalassemia in Nawabshah, Pakistan. The findings indicate that the majority of parents (63.68%) demonstrated poor knowledge regarding genetic inheritance, prevention, treatment modalities, and complications associated with Thalassemia. Only a minority of parents (36.72%) had good knowledge, highlighting significant gaps in understanding. Demographic factors such as low education, illiteracy (56%), rural residence (72.1%), poor economic status (84.2%), and female predominance (67.8%) were associated with lower levels of awareness. No significant differences were observed between male and female parents, suggesting that gender does not influence knowledge levels, whereas educational and socio-economic factors play a stronger role. These findings emphasize the urgent need for targeted educational programs and awareness campaigns to improve parental understanding of Thalassemia and support preventive and management strategies in high-burden area

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